

An Extension of Temporal Feature Selection

Hiroataka Niitsuma

Abstract

Temporal Feature Selection (TFS) efficiently selects moving-average-based features for time-series prediction by combining prefix-sum computation with L1 regularization. However, conventional TFS is limited to linear combinations of moving averages and cannot directly incorporate higher-order polynomial features such as variance and covariance terms.

In this study, we propose an extension of TFS that enables the inclusion of polynomial moving-average features up to a specified order. We formulate a unified feature space consisting of moving averages of polynomial terms and polynomial combinations of moving averages, and estimate their coefficients using Lasso regression. To mitigate the combinatorial growth of the feature space, we restrict candidate window sizes to powers of two, thereby preserving multi-scale information while reducing computational cost.

We further analyze alternative basis representations of candlestick data and show that the proposed `cdelta` representation tends to yield more stable and informative features. Experiments on U.S. stock data (AAPL, MSFT, and BAC) indicate that the proposed method often achieves performance comparable to or better than Lasso models based on standard technical indicators in terms of ROC-AUC and trading Sharpe ratio. Additional experiments on 98 tickers also suggest that a compact subset of selected price-volume interaction features can remain useful beyond the original three stocks, although their effectiveness depends on market regime.

These results suggest that polynomial extensions of moving-average-based feature spaces provide a compact and practically useful framework for financial time-series prediction.

1 Introduction

Accurate prediction of time-series data depends critically on the design and selection of informative features. This is particularly true for sequentially observed data such as sensor signals and financial time series, where the extraction of useful information from historical observations strongly affects predictive accuracy. Although price movements in financial markets often appear close to a random walk, it has also been reported that interactions between order flow and market response play an important role in price formation [?].

In this paper, we focus on Temporal Feature Selection (TFS) [7], a prior method for feature selection in time-series prediction. TFS can efficiently select moving-average-based features with very low computational cost. However, TFS cannot directly handle features involving polynomial expressions of order two or higher, such as covariances among multiple variables. We therefore extend TFS so that polynomially expressed features can also be incorporated. We compare the extended method with linear regression models based on widely used indicators in financial analysis, such as Bollinger Bands, Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD), and the Relative Strength Index (RSI).

2 Moving Averages of Time-Series Signals

Many features used for a time-series signal $x(t)$ are based on the moving average $M_w(x(t-g))$:

$$M_w(x(t-g)) = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{i=0}^{w-1} x(t-g-i)$$

where w is the window size and g is the lag. In financial data analysis, moving-average-based features such as Bollinger Bands, MACD, and RSI are widely used [8,14]. In image processing, moving averages are also frequently used to approximate wavelet-like features [13].

To select a moving average suitable for a given problem, one must generally search over two parameters: the window size w and the lag g . However, by using the *Prefix-Sum* technique [1], also known as an *integral image* in image processing [3,13], this problem can be reduced to searching only over w . Reducing the number of search parameters is one reason why moving-average-based features are widely used in practice.

If the target problem can be expressed as a linear regression problem, then feature selection can be performed by exploiting sparsity through Lasso regression [10]. In this study, we extend Temporal Feature Selection (TFS) [7], which combines Lasso regression with fast computation of moving-average features.

3 Extension to Higher-Order Features

Features expressed by quadratic forms, such as variance, are important in many applications. For example, Bollinger Bands are based on the standard deviation of a time-series signal. A feature representing the correlation structure between two variables x_i and x_j can be expressed by the following moving average:

$$\begin{aligned} M_w((x_i(t) - M_w(x_i(t))) \cdot (x_j(t) - M_w(x_j(t)))) \\ = M_w(x_i(t)x_j(t)) - M_w(x_i(t))M_w(x_j(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Thus, various useful features can be represented by combining moving averages of polynomial terms and polynomial combinations of moving averages.

TFS is based on restricting the prediction problem to linear regression and expressing various features through linear combinations of moving averages. Therefore, it cannot be straightforwardly extended to features expressed by quadratic or higher-order polynomial terms. In this paper, we propose a method that performs Lasso regression on the following model constructed from moving averages of polynomial terms and polynomial combinations of moving averages:

$$\hat{y}(t) = \beta \cdot \psi_{w_{\max}, r_{\max}}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d) \quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{w_{\max}, r_{\max}}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d) \\ = (\\ 1, \\ M_{w_1}(x_1(t)), M_{w_1}(x_2(t)), \dots, M_{w_1}(x_d(t)) \\ , M_{w_2}(x_1(t)), M_{w_2}(x_2(t)), \dots, M_{w_2}(x_d(t)), \dots \\ , M_{w_{\max}}(x_1(t)), M_{w_{\max}}(x_2(t)), \dots \\ , M_{w_{\max}}(x_d(t)), \\ M_{w_1}(x_1(t)x_1(t)), M_{w_1}(x_1(t)x_2(t)), \dots \\ , M_{w_1}(x_d(t)x_d(t)), \\ M_{w_2}(x_1(t)x_1(t)), M_{w_2}(x_1(t)x_2(t)), \dots \\ , M_{w_{\max}}(x_d(t)^2), \dots, M_{w_{\max}}(x_d(t)^3), \dots \\ , M_{w_{\max}}(x_d(t)^{r_{\max}}), \\ M_{w_1}(x_1(t))M_{w_1}(x_1(t)), \\ M_{w_1}(x_1(t))M_{w_1}(x_2(t)), \dots \\ , M_{w_1}(x_d(t))M_{w_1}(x_d(t)), \\ M_{w_1}(x_1(t))M_{w_2}(x_1(t)), \dots \\ M_{w_1}(x_1(t))M_{w_2}(x_1(t)^2), \dots \\ M_{w_1}(x_3(t)^2)M_{w_2}(x_5(t)^3), \dots \\ M_{w_{\max}}(x_d(t))^2, \dots, M_{w_{\max}}(x_d(t))^3, \dots \\ , M_{w_{\max}}(x_d(t))^{r_{\max}} \\) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

This vector enumerates combinations of moving averages of polynomial terms and polynomial combinations of moving averages up to maximum degree r_{\max} . The

coefficient vector β is optimized by Lasso regression. The set

$$\{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{\max}\}$$

denotes the candidate moving-average window sizes. By solving this regression problem with Lasso, if, for example, the moving average of variance is important, then the corresponding coefficient is expected to take a nonzero value. As in TFS, this formulation avoids the need to explicitly search over the lag parameter g .

4 Restriction to Power-of-Two Window Sizes

When higher-order features are considered as in (3), the feature vector ψ becomes extremely large. As a result, Lasso regression requires a large amount of computation. To mitigate this issue, we restrict window sizes w_i to powers of two:

$$w_i = 2^{i-1}$$

In time-series models, features with longer lags tend to be less important. Accordingly, methods have been proposed that solve weighted regression problems so that features with larger lags are less likely to be selected [5]. Using weights proportional to $1/2^{\text{lag}}$ is expected to provide good performance. The proposed restriction to power-of-two window sizes produces a feature set that becomes sparser with increasing lag at roughly the rate of $1/2^{\text{lag}}$. In this sense, the proposed method can also be viewed as an extension of lag-weighted methods [5].

5 Basis Vectors of Moving Averages and Candlestick Data

Prefix-Sum and TFS introduce relationships through which one moving average can be expressed as a linear combination of others. That is, they implicitly define a vector space of moving averages. Equation (3) enumerates candidates that can serve as basis vectors for this vector space when polynomial features such as (1) are included. Because the computational cost would otherwise become excessive, we exclude polynomial terms that are expected to be unimportant.

Many financial datasets are represented as candlesticks. Here we discuss basis representations of candlestick data.

Candlestick data are 4-dimensional vectors (open, high, low, close). These four values are often very close to one another. Therefore, instead of using them directly, one often uses representations of the form

$$(\text{high/close}, \text{low/close}, \text{open/close}, \text{close})$$

which express changes relative to a reference value together with the reference value itself [9]. Given that we can exploit the vector-space structure of moving averages, we consider the following six 4-dimensional representations and their union `all`.

- `cdelta`

$$\begin{pmatrix} \text{highc} \\ \text{lowc} \\ \text{openc} \\ \text{close} \end{pmatrix}^T = \begin{pmatrix} \text{high} - \text{close} \\ \text{low} - \text{close} \\ \text{open} - \text{close} \\ \text{close} \end{pmatrix}^T$$

- `odelta`

$$\begin{pmatrix} \text{higho} \\ \text{lowo} \\ \text{openc} \\ \text{close} \end{pmatrix}^T = \begin{pmatrix} \text{high} - \text{open} \\ \text{low} - \text{open} \\ \text{open} - \text{close} \\ \text{close} \end{pmatrix}^T$$

- `clog`

$$\begin{pmatrix} \text{highlc} \\ \text{lowlc} \\ \text{openlc} \\ \text{closel} \end{pmatrix}^T = \begin{pmatrix} \log(\text{high}/\text{close}) \\ \log(\text{low}/\text{close}) \\ \log(\text{open}/\text{close}) \\ \log(\text{close}) \end{pmatrix}^T$$

- `olog`

$$\begin{pmatrix} \text{highlo} \\ \text{lowlo} \\ \text{openlc} \\ \text{closel} \end{pmatrix}^T = \begin{pmatrix} \log(\text{high}/\text{open}) \\ \log(\text{low}/\text{open}) \\ \log(\text{open}/\text{close}) \\ \log(\text{close}) \end{pmatrix}^T$$

- `crate`

$$\begin{pmatrix} \text{highcrate} \\ \text{lowcrate} \\ \text{opencrate} \\ \text{close} \end{pmatrix}^T = \begin{pmatrix} \text{high}/\text{close} - 1 \\ \text{low}/\text{close} - 1 \\ \text{open}/\text{close} - 1 \\ \text{close} \end{pmatrix}^T$$

- `orate`

$$\begin{pmatrix} \text{highrate} \\ \text{lowrate} \\ \text{closerate} \\ \text{close} \end{pmatrix}^T = \begin{pmatrix} \text{high}/\text{open} - 1 \\ \text{low}/\text{open} - 1 \\ \text{close}/\text{open} - 1 \\ \text{close} \end{pmatrix}^T$$

- `all`

$$\text{all} = \text{cdelta} \cup \text{odelta} \cup \text{clog} \cup \text{olog} \cup \text{crate} \cup \text{orate}$$

The following relationships hold between `cdelta` and `odelta`:

$$\begin{aligned} M_w(\text{high} - \text{close}) - M_w(\text{open} - \text{close}) \\ &= M_w(\text{high} - \text{open}) \\ M_w(\text{low} - \text{close}) - M_w(\text{open} - \text{close}) \\ &= M_w(\text{low} - \text{open}) \end{aligned}$$

That is, the TFS result obtained from `cdelta` can be linearly transformed into the `odelta` representation. Therefore, `cdelta` and `odelta` are expected to yield similar TFS results. A similar relationship also holds between `clog` and `olog`, so a similar tendency can be expected. Features similar to `cdelta` and `odelta` were used in [12], where they are argued to be suitable for representing trend changes [12].

Features similar to `olog` were used in [9,11], where they are argued to have properties that make candlestick data easier to handle [9].

The `crate` and `orate` representations are sometimes used because they are easy to interpret [4]. However, unlike `cdelta` and `odelta`, no analogous linear relationship exists between `crate` and `orate`. Although these representations may be less suitable for TFS, we include them for comparison.

5.1 Technical Indicators

Raw candlestick data are often difficult to use directly, so many transformed representations have been used in financial analysis. Examples include a 14-day average of (previous day's close - today's high) or a 14-day average of (previous day's close - today's close), among many others. The `ta` library [2] implements approximately 90 such transformations commonly used in financial data analysis. These candlestick-based derived features are commonly called *technical indicators*. Analysis using only technical indicators is referred to as *technical analysis*. For comparison, we also conduct experiments in which technical indicators are used as explanatory variables in a linear TFS-style Lasso framework. We denote this comparison method by **ta-Lasso**.

6 Experiments

A related study using Lasso regression is [14]. That study applies technical-analysis features [2] to Lasso regression for feature selection. We follow a similar experimental setting to evaluate the proposed method. Specifically, we consider a binary classification problem in which the task is to predict whether the next-day stock price of AAPL, MSFT, and BAC will increase or decrease. We use the same train/test periods as in [14], shown in Table 6.

The target variable y is defined as the sign of the next-day close-to-close return:

$$y = \text{label}(t) = \text{sign}(\text{close}(t+1) - \text{close}(t))$$

In this study we focus on the vector-space structure of moving averages, and therefore consider linear regression rather than logistic regression, which involves a nonlinear transformation. The explanatory variables depend on the chosen input representation, which we call `ohlcmode`. When `ohlcmode` is `cdelta`, we solve the following linear regression problem:

$$\hat{y} = \beta \cdot \psi_{w_{\max}, r_{\max}}(\text{highc}, \text{lowc}, \text{openc}, \text{close}, \text{volume})$$

where `volume` denotes trading volume. For other modes such as `odelta` and `clog`, analogous linear regression problems are solved using Lasso.

The search space of moving-average features is defined by $w_{\max} \in \{2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64\}$ and $r_{\max} \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. We evaluate all combinations. When $r_{\max} = 1$, the method reduces to the normal TFS without polynomial extension.

As a baseline, we also apply Lasso regression to approximately 90 technical indicators provided by the

ta library [2]. We denote this comparison baseline by **ta-Lasso**.

For cross-validation, we use a time-order-preserving split (TimeSeriesSplit), denoted by `tv`, and a KFold split, denoted by `cv`. The number of splits is set to five. The Lasso regularization coefficient and the meta-parameters w_{\max} and r_{\max} are selected by minimizing squared error in cross-validation.

Table 7 shows the experimental results. `#feat` denotes the number of selected features. w_{\max} and r_{\max} are the values determined by cross-validation. `sharpe ratio` denotes the Sharpe ratio obtained when the output of the Lasso regression is used as a trading signal. `LSTMauc` denotes the ROC-AUC obtained by training an LSTM using only the explanatory variables selected by Lasso.

The **ta-Lasso** results with `split=cv` correspond to an experiment analogous to the `LSTMTI` setting in [14]. We were unable to reproduce the high ROC-AUC values reported for `LSTMTI` in [14]. When technical indicators are used as explanatory variables, the number of selected features often becomes `#feat = 0`. This suggests that technical indicators alone may be insufficient to predict these stocks.

In most cases, the best results are obtained with the `cdelta` representation. Although `odelta` is best in some cases, its values are usually not very different from those of `cdelta`. When focusing on accuracy, `olog` sometimes gives favorable results. In terms of `#feat`, `clog` tends to select many features, suggesting that it may be prone to overfitting when the truly informative features are limited. In many cases, `cdelta` performs better than **ta-Lasso**. The polynomially extended TFS with `cdelta` tends to outperform standard technical analysis. When $r_{\max} = 1$, the method reduces to the normal TFS without polynomial extension, and $r_{\max} = 1$ was selected as best only in the `BAC-cv` case. This suggests that the polynomial extension of TFS is useful in many cases.

Table 4 lists the selected features for the settings that yield the best ROC-AUC for each stock. When the moving-average length is $w = 1$, redundant polynomial terms satisfying

$$M_1(x \cdot y) = M_1(x) \cdot M_1(y)$$

are removed. In many settings for `BAC`, the number of selected features becomes `#feat = 0`, suggesting that non-candlestick information may be important for `BAC`. `MSFT` and `AAPL` select the same features. Among the selected features for `MSFT` and `AAPL`, several terms represent interactions between price variation and volume, such as

$$M_1(\text{lowc}) \cdot M_2(\text{volume})$$

These can also be interpreted as features related to the interaction between large orders and liquidity [?]. Such large-order-related features may be useful for a wide range of financial datasets. We refer to this 5-dimensional feature set as `cdelta22`, and examine its usefulness in Section 6.1.

Table 5 shows a subset of the selected features when all representations are combined in `all`. According to Table 7, `all` is inferior to `cdelta` for `MSFT` and `AAPL`, but still yields reasonable values even for `BAC`. Thus, `all` may provide more stable results. However, the selected features of `all` do not include `cdelta`-type features and instead are dominated by `crate` and `orate`. One possible reason is that these interpretable ratio-based features are widely observed and implicitly used by many human traders, even though they do not exploit the vector-space property of moving averages that TFS relies on.

We also report `LSTMauc`, obtained by training an LSTM using only the selected features in Table 4. This follows the procedure proposed in [14]. In all cases, the LSTM performs worse than Lasso. This may indicate that moving-average-based sparse features are not well suited for combination with LSTMs.

The Sharpe ratio obtained by trading on the output signal of Lasso regression is shown in the `sharpe` column. A related study that also computes Sharpe ratios using daily features is [6]. That study reports Sharpe ratios for 2010–2015 that are roughly between -1.5 and 1.5 . Compared with that range, the values obtained here, roughly between 1.3 and 2.6, are favorable.

Figures 1, 2, and 3 show results obtained by fixing w_{\max} and r_{\max} and selecting the Lasso regularization parameter by minimizing cross-validated squared error. When $r_{\max} = 1$, the method reduces to the normal TFS without polynomial extension. In many cases, $r_{\max} = 2$ performs better than $r_{\max} = 1$, which supports the usefulness of the polynomial extension. When $r_{\max} > 2$, performance tends to deteriorate. Therefore, we search only within $r_{\max} \leq 3$. For $w_{\max} > 32$, substantial performance improvements are generally not observed, and in some cases performance deteriorates. Therefore, we search only within $w_{\max} \leq 64$. For `BAC`, many `ohlcmode` settings yield nearly identical values, suggesting that the choice of candlestick representation has limited impact for this stock.

6.1 Usefulness of `cdelta22`

Here we investigate whether the `cdelta22` feature set is also useful beyond the three stocks above. Using the 98 tickers shown in Table 2, we conducted experiments on daily data from 2021/3/1 to 2026/3/1. The last 20% of each series was used as the test set. A trading threshold maximizing Sharpe ratio was selected within the training data, after which the model was refit on the entire training set and the test Sharpe ratio was evaluated.

Table 1 summarizes the results. Across all 98 tickers, the mean test Sharpe ratio was 0.251 and the median was 0.071. Fifty-one tickers had positive Sharpe, 31 had negative Sharpe, and 16 had zero Sharpe. The best-performing ticker was `GLD` (test Sharpe = 3.486), while the worst was `ROP` (test Sharpe = -2.034).

Table 1: Summary of linear threshold optimization over 98 tickers

Metric	Value
Number of tickers	98
Mean test Sharpe	0.251
Median test Sharpe	0.071
Number of tickers with test Sharpe > 0	51
Number of tickers with test Sharpe < 0	31
Number of tickers with test Sharpe = 0	16
Best ticker (GLD), test Sharpe	3.486
Worst ticker (ROP), test Sharpe	-2.034

Table 2: Tickers used in the linear-threshold optimization experiment (98 tickers)

ticker symbols
NVDA, AAPL, MSFT, AMZN, GOOGL, AVGO, TSLA, WMT, ASML, MU, COST, NFLX, AMD, PLTR, CSCO, LRCX, AMAT, TMUS, LIN, PEP, INTC, AMGN, TXN, KLAC, GILD, ISRG, ADI, SHOP, HON, QCOM, PDD, BKNG, VRTX, PANW, CMCSA, SBUX, ADBE, INTU, MELI, CRWD, WDC, MAR, STX, ADP, SNPS, REGN, MNST, CDNS, CTAS, ORLY, CSX, ABNB, DASH, MDLZ, AEP, PCAR, MRVL, ROST, BKR, FTNT, MPWR, NXPI, FAST, IDXX, EA, FANG, EXC, XEL, ADSK, CCEP, ALNY, MSTR, ODFL, MCHP, DDOG, KDP, PYPL, TTWO, WDAY, ROP, CPRT, INSM, AXON, PAYX, CTSH, CHTR, KHC, DXCM, ZS, VRSK, CSGP, TEAM, SPY, QQQ, DIA, GLD, SLV, SOXL

Five tickers achieved a test Sharpe ratio of at least 2: NVDA, MU, STX, GLD, and SOXL. Table 3 shows the groups by Sharpe-ratio threshold.

Table 3: Tickers grouped by test Sharpe threshold in the linear-threshold optimization experiment

Condition	Count	ticker symbols
$2 \leq \text{test Sharpe}$	5	NVDA, MU, STX, GLD, SOXL
$1 \leq \text{test Sharpe} < 2$	11	GOOGL, AVGO, CSCO, AMAT, KLAC, GILD, CSX, MPWR, EA, ALNY, SLV
$0 < \text{test Sharpe} < 1$	35	AAPL, AMZN, TSLA, WMT, NFLX, AMD, LRCX, LIN, PEP, AMGN, TXN, ISRG, ADI, SHOP, PDD, VRTX, WDC, MAR, REGN, MNST, CDNS, MDLZ, AEP, PCAR, BKR, FAST, XEL, CCEP, MCHP, DDOG, INSM, AXON, PAYX, CHTR, DIA
test Sharpe = 0	16	ASML, HON, QCOM, CMCSA, ADBE, MELI, DASH, ROST, FANG, EXC, ODFL, KDP, PYPL, CTSH, KHC, ZS
$-1 < \text{test Sharpe} < 0$	19	COST, PLTR, TMUS, INTC, BKNG, PANW, CRWD, SNPS, ORLY, ABNB, MRVL, FTNT, NXPI, ADSK, MSTR, TTWO, DXCM, CSGP, QQQ
test Sharpe ≤ -1	12	MSFT, SBUX, INTU, ADP, CTAS, IDXX, WDAY, ROP, CPRT, VRSK, TEAM, SPY

In this experiment, software-related stocks tended to exhibit lower Sharpe ratios than other sectors. One possible explanation is that during the test period, the rapid progress of generative AI models, especially the release of the Claude series by Anthropic, drastically changed the competitive environment in the software industry. In contrast, assets less directly related to software tended to show better Sharpe values.

These results suggest that the `cdelta22` features may be vulnerable to large environmental regime changes, but can still be useful when such shifts are absent or weaker. The Pine Script for GLD, which achieved the best result among the evaluated assets, has been published on TradingView at <https://www.tradingview.com/script/7yIh8gog-GLD-Machine-Learning-Strategy-Lasso-Features-Selection/>.

Table 4: Selected features

ticker	#feat	selected features
MSFT	6	$M_2(\text{volume})$
		$M_1(\text{openc})$
		$M_1(\text{highc} \cdot \text{lowc})$
		$M_2(\text{openc}) \cdot M_2(\text{volume})$
		$M_1(\text{lowc}) \cdot M_2(\text{volume})$
AAPL	6	$M_2(\text{volume})$
		$M_1(\text{openc})$
		$M_1(\text{highc} \cdot \text{lowc})$
		$M_2(\text{openc}) \cdot M_2(\text{volume})$
		$M_1(\text{lowc}) \cdot M_2(\text{volume})$
BAC	2	$M_4(\text{volume})$
		$M_1(\text{openc})$

Table 5: Selected features for the best `tv+all` setting on MSFT

ticker	#feat	selected features
MSFT	10	$M_1(\text{openrate})$
		$M_1(\text{highrate} \cdot \text{highrate})$
		$M_1(\text{highrate} \cdot \text{highlo})$
		$M_1(\text{closerate})$
		$M_1(\text{highrate} \cdot \text{highlc})$
		$M_1(\text{highlc} \cdot \text{highlo})$
		$M_1(\text{openlc})$
		$M_2(\text{closerate}) \cdot M_2(\text{volume})$
		$M_2(\text{highrate}) \cdot M_2(\text{volume})$
		$M_2(\text{openlc}) \cdot M_2(\text{volume})$
		$M_2(\text{highlo}) \cdot M_2(\text{volume})$

7 Conclusion

We proposed an extension of Temporal Feature Selection (TFS) that enables the use of features expressed by polynomial terms of order two or higher, such as covariance-like interactions, in moving-average-based feature selection for time-series data. The resulting sparse linear models tend to achieve performance comparable to or better than linear regression models based on technical indicators commonly used in financial analysis.

Because TFS provides a vector-space structure in which moving averages can be represented through linear combinations of other moving averages, we also compared multiple candlestick representations from this viewpoint. The experimental results suggest that the `cdelta` representation is generally the most effective among the tested alternatives.

Overall, the results indicate that polynomial extensions of moving-average feature spaces are a promising direction for compact and interpretable financial time-

References

- [1] Guy E. Blelloch. Prefix sums and their applications. Technical report, Carnegie Mellon University, 2004.
- [2] Darío López Padial (bukosabino). ta: Technical analysis library using pandas and numpy. <https://github.com/bukosabino/ta>, 2018. GitHub repository, <https://github.com/bukosabino/ta>.
- [3] Frank C. Crow. Summed-area tables for texture mapping. In *SIGGRAPH*, 1984.
- [4] Mouna Ben Daoud, Manel Hamdi, Rabeb Younes, and Dhouka Oueldoubey. Optimized feature selection based on machine learning models for robust stock market prediction. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Scientific Studies*, 8(3):5086–5099, Jun. 2025.
- [5] Tahir Dikheel and Alaa Yaseen. Robust lag weighted lasso for time series model. *Journal of Modern Applied Statistical Methods*, 19(1), 2021.
- [6] Thomas Fischer and Christopher Krauss. Deep learning with long short-term memory networks for financial market predictions. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 270(2):654–669, 2018.
- [7] Shohei Hido and Tetsuro Morimura. Temporal feature selection for time-series prediction. In *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR2012)*, pages 3557–3560, 2012.
- [8] Htet Htet Htun, Michael Biehl, and Nicolai Petkov. Survey of feature selection and extraction techniques for stock market prediction. *Financial Innovation*, 9(26), 2023.
- [9] Wenyang Huang, Huiwen Wang, and Shanshan Wang. Dimension reduction of open-high-low-close data in candlestick chart based on pseudo-pca. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2103.16908*, March 2021. arXiv:2103.16908v1.
- [10] Shuangge Ma and Peter J. Bickel. Variable selection in nonparametric additive models. *The Annals of Statistics*, 39(1):152–179, 2011.
- [11] Peter Molnár. Properties of range-based volatility estimators. Technical report, Norwegian School of Economics and Business Administration (NHH), August 2010. Manuscript dated August 5, 2010.
- [12] Yun-Cheng Tsai, Jun-Hao Chen, and Chun-Chieh Wang. Encoding candlesticks as images for patterns classification using convolutional neural networks. *CoRR*, abs/1901.05237, 2019. arXiv preprint.
- [13] Paul Viola and Michael Jones. Rapid object detection using a boosted cascade of simple features. In *Proceedings of the 2001 IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition. CVPR 2001*, volume 1, 2001.
- [14] Junwen Yang, Yunmin Wang, and Xiang Li. Prediction of stock price direction using the LASSO-LSTM model combines technical indicators and financial sentiment analysis. *PeerJ Computer Science*, 8, 2022.

Table 6: The training sets and the testing sets from MSFT, AAPL and BAC.

Company	Training set	Testing set
MSFT	2015/12/21–2018/12/02	2018/12/21–2019/12/31
AAPL	2015/12/08–2018/12/06	2018/12/07–2019/12/04
BAC	2014/11/18–2018/03/02	2018/03/05–2019/03/13

A Use of Large Language Models

A.1 Generation of Polynomial Bases

We attempted to use ChatGPT to generate a program that constructs the set of polynomial terms in (3). However, as of October 2025, we were unable to generate such a program correctly using ChatGPT alone. For example, it failed to generate a set of polynomial terms that included expressions such as

$$M_{w_1}(x_1(t)) \cdot M_{w_2}(x_3(t)^2)$$

As of February 2025, ChatGPT became capable of partially generating such a program. However, this may have been influenced by the fact that a large amount of information related to this study had already been provided to ChatGPT. Even as of February 2026, constructing a correct program for generating the polynomial set in (3) still required several rounds of human correction of errors in ChatGPT-generated code.

Table 7: Comparison between the proposed method and TA-Lasso for each stock

ticker	split	ohlmode	ROC-AUC	Acc.	#feat	w_{\max}	r_{\max}	sharpe ratio	LSTMauc
MSFT	tv	ta-Lasso	0.5000	0.5891	0	—	—	—	—
		r1-best(orate)	0.5318	0.5698	4	2	1	—	—
		all	0.5454	0.5775	15	2	2	—	—
		cdelta	0.5639	0.5504	6	2	2	2.5781	0.5448
		odelta	0.5321	0.5775	16	8	2	—	—
		clog	0.4913	0.5388	35	8	2	—	—
		olog	0.5458	0.5698	4	2	2	—	—
		orate	0.5166	0.5853	14	2	3	—	—
	cv	ta-Lasso	0.5464	0.5736	4	2	2	—	—
		r1-best(all)	0.5554	0.5543	6	—	—	2.2540	0.5064
		all	0.5135	0.5388	10	8	1	—	—
		cdelta	0.5236	0.5620	65	8	2	—	—
		odelta	0.5296	0.5504	21	8	2	—	—
		clog	0.5349	0.5775	13	2	3	—	—
olog		0.4937	0.5388	35	8	2	—	—	
orate		0.5119	0.5698	24	8	2	—	—	
AAPL	tv	ta-Lasso	0.5460	0.5840	2	—	—	1.9204	0.4774
		r1-best(orate)	0.5348	0.5720	4	2	1	—	—
		all	0.5432	0.5640	25	2	2	—	—
		cdelta	0.5495	0.5480	6	2	2	2.1797	0.5135
		odelta	0.5202	0.5520	19	2	3	—	—
		clog	0.5009	0.5160	40	8	2	—	—
		olog	0.5279	0.5880	12	2	3	—	—
		orate	0.5214	0.5720	13	2	3	—	—
	cv	ta-Lasso	0.5287	0.5800	12	2	3	—	—
		r1-best(orate)	0.5401	0.5400	7	—	—	—	—
		all	0.5209	0.5360	18	16	1	—	—
		cdelta	0.5414	0.5520	85	8	2	—	—
		odelta	0.4937	0.5280	46	8	2	—	—
		clog	0.5283	0.5560	24	8	2	—	—
olog		0.5025	0.5240	34	8	2	—	—	
orate		0.5176	0.5600	29	8	2	—	—	
BAC	tv	ta-Lasso	0.5194	0.5320	27	8	2	—	—
		r1-best(cdelta)	0.5000	0.5504	0	—	—	—	—
		all	0.5778	0.5698	2	2	1	—	—
		cdelta	0.5000	0.5504	0	—	—	—	—
		odelta	0.5000	0.5504	0	—	—	—	—
		clog	0.4956	0.5504	1	32	3	—	—
		olog	0.5000	0.5504	0	—	—	—	—
		orate	0.5000	0.5504	0	—	—	—	—
	cv	ta-Lasso	0.5000	0.5504	0	—	—	—	—
		r1-best(cdelta)	0.5000	0.5504	0	—	—	—	—
		all	0.5781	0.5543	1	4	1	—	—
		cdelta	0.5800	0.5388	4	8	1	—	—
		odelta	0.5781	0.5543	1	4	1	—	—
		clog	0.5808	0.5543	2	4	1	1.3377	—
olog		0.5795	0.5465	1	4	1	—	—	
orate		0.5800	0.5388	2	8	1	—	—	
	crate	0.5795	0.5426	1	8	1	—	—	
	orate	0.5795	0.5465	2	8	1	—	—	

Figure 1: MSFT

Figure 2: AAPL

Figure 3: BAC

A.2 Application to Image Processing

TFS can be regarded as an application of integral images. Therefore, feature selection for images analogous to TFS should in principle also be possible. When implementing a Python program that applies TFS to images, it is essential to use the integral-image functionality in OpenCV, because numerical computation with Python for loops is extremely slow.

We also attempted to use ChatGPT to construct such an image-processing program. However, as of October 2025, we were unable to obtain a correct image feature-selection program simply by instructing ChatGPT to extend or apply TFS. One possible reason is that the original TFS paper [7] did not cite literature related to integral images and did not explicitly discuss the relation between TFS and integral images.

When a human first provided an OpenCV-based code example and deliberately avoided mentioning the relation to TFS, ChatGPT generated a Python program shown elsewhere. That program was a reasonable extension of TFS to image processing and implemented person detection using Lasso regression.

Even as of February 2026, this issue had not been fully resolved. At that time, ChatGPT could generate partially correct code, but it was difficult to specify the errors precisely through natural-language instructions. As a result, the workflow used in October 2025 still required less effort.